

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Katunda**FIRST NAME:** Kahilo Jose**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US.*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is:

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5 key concepts :

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 7-12)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34-39)
4. The style (EUCLID 2024, 40)
5. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)

KEY ACADEMIC JOURNEY AT EUCLID UNIVERSITY

1) INTRODUCTION

Mastery of the first module of the course at Euclid University is the key to success in the academic journey.

I am working on the first module of the course ACA-401D at Euclid University because this module is an entry point for students at Euclid University, and I encourage all students to go through this chapter.

The objective of this first module is to allow students to have the essentials or be oriented on how to write a good academic essay, respect punctuation, avoid plagiarism, have a good style, and make sure British and American English speakers find themselves while writing and reading. A traveler prepares his trip the same way academic work requires preparedness.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The essay covers a certain basic step to follow to write a good academic essay. Time needs to be dedicated. Whatever the skill, think well and start very early, not in a hurry to write. It is always important to start early. This would allow me to refine the work, ask multiple questions that have to be answered and have a well-established plan to properly arrange the ideas and the steps to follow. A work without research is assimilated to a vase of water without any water. Knowing how to arrange/organize ideas is very important, as I have to talk to myself and convey my ideas to others.

Knowing how to write is an important skill; it is the art of expressing one's thoughts and one's ideas and transmitting them to others. One can have ideas, but these ideas are not transmitted to others in writing and can fly away. Don't we say that the writings remain, and the words fly away? I must leave the traces of my thoughts; I must write to show that I'm the author, which is why, throughout this course, I must produce a paper to show that I have understood the steps, and I must write to complete my thesis; it is not an oral thesis but a document that would be used for my reference, but also that will be used by others. This is how we always refer to the ideas of others; if the latter do not have research, arrange ideas, and write, I must not today enrich myself intellectually; hence the need to refer to the ideas of others and to write well, allowing readers to grasp the messages, ideas, or knowledge that I have to transmit, taking into consideration the good use of punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 7-12).

Essays give you the opportunity to demonstrate a wide range of skills.

3) PUNCTUATION

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knowledge that I have to transmit, taking into consideration the good use of punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15-23).

a) Periods

Each writing has a period, as each sentence must have an end to give meaning to the writing. The period finishes a sentence; this can be a testament or the end of a message. As everything has a beginning and an end, the sentence also has an end, so by putting, for example, a period at the end of a phase, it marks the end of a period. The period can also be vertical to show the end of the enumerating sentences; putting a period at the end can also mean the period, contrary to the commas.

b) Commas

The commas are very important; they allow me to avoid mistakes in the reading because the reader must know where the sentence ends or how to separate it while keeping the meaning of the sentence. It is true that I have to explain several thoughts in a long sentence, but I have to arrange them, connect them to each other while keeping the meaning of the sentences, and show the end of my thoughts. The comma can also be used in various phases or forms to introduce, separate two or more adjectives, separate nouns, clarify comments, oppose nouns, repetitions, put in parenthesis, and interject, but the semicolon is more important because it sometimes gives me a large interval in the continuation of the sentence.

c) Semi-colons

Writing requires a certain logic; several words can have the same meaning but link to each other; the semicolons help to make a link between different sentences that have a certain logic of their meanings; these sentences can depend on the others or without depend on but follow a certain grammatical logic and complete the sentence better. The use of semicolons reflects the logic in the sub-clause of a text, so it is not a new concept.

d) Colons

The colons are, therefore, not a new concept; they often introduce the sub-clauses in the punctuation logically depending on the first concepts; the colon introduces, explains a series of elements, clarifies, and amplifies the previous ideas in the introduction, but this is not a question that I ask myself.

e) Question Marks

The mark question is very important in punctuation; it does not show the period, nor the comma or semicolons or colonists, the questions that I ask myself in the punctuation and sometimes to remove the ambiguity of a situation that I doubt or that I must know.

f) Exclamation Points

Exclamation marks can be used but are often rarely used in academic work. They can be noted in the citation of the titles of a subject, the same as hyphens and dashes, which are used in some contexts.

g) Hyphens and Dashes

The use of hyphens and dashes should be used with caution so as not to produce work with multiple hyphens and dashes that can be seen by readers as laziness or limits in thinking. One must know how and when to use them, e.g., using hyphens when it comes to the adjective that follows nouns and not in noun sentences. On the other hand, not m-dash but rather n-dash is used in pairs instead of a dot or in parentheses. It can also be used to link authors and their works.

h) Parentheses and Brackets

Writing is also about knowing how to express the thoughts of others. Thought can be expressed in various ways, such as by quotations, parentheses, and brackets. An author cannot refrain from quoting the words or wisdom of others. Writing is complementarity while asserting the thoughts of others. The use of parentheses and brackets in this essay allows me to understand the interrupted ideas of a sentence. It is also like commas, which separate the closest ideas from the main ideas, while sometimes the parenthesis, the ideas that are not close or the abbreviations that explain the author's ideas; on the other hand, the brackets explain the quotes to demonstrate the sources, e.g., names, dates, and other information relating to the author that are not listed or cited.

i) Slashes

Two words can have the same meaning; the use of slashes shows the ease of the language and proves the sufficiency of mastery of its subject; the slash is less used in writing but several times in fractions or division in mathematics and in searches on the internet to identify sites; often these double slashes are recurrent in the use of slashes in writing. Computer scientists are very careful about identifying sites for the veracity and reliability of information on the Internet.

j) Quotation Marks

Each university shows its students how to make citations. As far as I'm concerned, I refer to the quotations of the University of EUCLID with Professor Gulma. It is very important to refer to the work of others or quote a sentence from an author; it gives credit to your work. The citation can be in different languages, but it must be cited so as not to distort or to express the author's idea badly, which is why, in some cases, it is always necessary to ask the author's permission before making a quotation because some quotations can be restrictive.

k) Apostrophes

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l) Multiple Punctuation Mark

It is true that I have talked about punctuation and its use; this gives me guidance during the elaboration of my thesis, but it turns out that sometimes, we can use both punctuations in the context of omission or in the case of other punctuation marks, it is also noticeable the use of two or more punctuations when saving the documents in word on the computer. Punctuation explains the correct use of various punctuation, as shown above.

4) PLAGIARISM

Intellectual honesty is the art of living. I must give credit to others who have had time to reflect on some issue or reflection, so it is important to avoid plagiarism by referring to someone's account without citing the author. Why is it very important to refer to statistics, data, and sources to enrich one's work? Citing the works of an author would allow you to convey the messages and also enrich your skills or knowledge (EUCLID 2024, 34-39). The information needs to be analyzed, so it is necessary to know where this information comes from and for what the quote or information. Plagiarism is an academic offense that can have consequences. To avoid this, I should always cite the author and make a reference. The reference can be in the text or list the quotations to say what the author said. It is important to avoid a long quotation and know how to paraphrase a text; know what to quote and what not to quote in the case, for example, of information that is known or sheltered by everyone. In addition, you need to know how to make a reference while knowing where to place the name of the author and the format to follow, for example,

a book, newspaper, web page, or footnotes, In the case of a website, if there is no date associated with the specific matter of the citation, then the citation should list the date when the website was last modified or last updated after the URL. If these indicators are unavailable, use the date on which the site was last visited (The Bluebook 2010, 24-25) while having knowledge of how to link sentences or transitions, such as, Nevertheless, on the one hand, on the other hand, in spite of this, for this reason, as a result, furthermore, furthermore...

5) THE STYLE

Every document must have a style; readers nevertheless know the author's style to show consistency. The style can be a way of writing, purely technical, commercial, or business world, journalistic style, or media or newspapers. How to impress your readers with different writing styles (Manvi 2020). Style is a very important element that defines being or can be defining what is consistent or appreciated. Even in the life of human beings, it is important to encourage them to have a lifestyle or a way of life. Having this lifestyle would help some people to follow or enjoy. This is also how one can imitate or learn a style. Style is also invited into publishing, in companies, on websites...

Why have a style of writing? It is an element of appreciation of coherence and consistency; likewise, when it comes to the style of the English language, there are multiple styles of English. EUCLID suggests the turban style of Chicago and British or American English; a document without a style used would create debates of substance and, in forms, debates of appreciation, even on grammar and vocabulary punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 40). Moreover, English does not have many problems in terms of punctuation compared to the French language. In the next chapter, we will see the difference between American English and British English.

6) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

The art of speaking, pronouncing, and writing is very important; through language analysis and skill, it is often easy to detect a person's style or handwriting. This chapter would allow us to see the difference between American English and British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32).

The use of American and British English dominates the world currently, but American English has taken off over British English. This is due to American influence, population, economy, technology, rapid development, global expansionism, and geopolitics that are positioning the USA on the world stage.

These two styles are often used, but the standards differentiate them. Sometimes, the two styles have the same name but different pronunciation or the same pronunciation but different name, the same terminology but different name and pronunciation, the same word but different meanings, the use of grammar, syntax, punctuation, and other common

usage, the same concept but different term or expression, and sometimes the same word but different style.

It is also important to mention the difference between the use of American and British English in the reference texts of scientific work.

7) CONCLUSION

It is a privilege to take the doctoral course at Euclid University; this long journey of life begins to understand the path I must take. To better prepare me for this course, I tried to understand writing steps so that this module course would allow me to have the essentials or be oriented on how to write a good academic essay, taking into account the respect of punctuation, avoid plagiarism, have a good style, and make sure that British and American English speakers find themselves in my writing and reading.

The steps to writing a good academic essay are very important. Knowing how to write is an important aspect. It is the art of expressing one's thoughts and one's ideas and transmitting them to others. One can have ideas, but these ideas are not transmitted to others in writing. Don't we say that the writings remain, and the words fly away? We urge readers to leave the traces of their thoughts. Transmitting knowledge requires respect for writing art and good use of punctuation. It is not a question of writing as I want but also having a sense of judgment in writing by listening carefully to the sounds of my phrases and the right pronunciation; some rules are clear, but the others no longer have but depend on certain judgment and hearing. The use of punctuation is very important to keep the meaning of sentences; the sentence must have a period to show that the sentence has a period or an end; the commas, which allow the reader to avoid mistakes, and semicolons help to make a link between different sentences that have a certain logic of their meanings. The colonists explain a series of elements and clarify and amplify the previous ideas in the introduction, but this is not a question that one asks. Question marks, the questions that one asks oneself in punctuation and sometimes to remove the equivocation; exclamation points, often used rarely in an academic work, as well as hyphens and dashes; the use of hyphens and dashes must be used with caution to not produce a work with multiple hyphens and dashes that can be glimpsed to readers as in the form of laziness or limits in reflection. Parentheses and brackets. The use of parentheses and brackets in this essay allows me to understand the interrupted ideas of a sentence. Slashes, which show the ease of the language and prove the sufficiency of mastery of its subject, computer scientists are very careful about identifying sites for the veracity and reliability of information on the internet. Quotation Marks. Each university shows its students how to make citations; as far as I am concerned, I refer to the quotations of the Euclid University with Professor Gulma. It is very important to refer to the work of others or quote a sentence from an author; this gives credit to your work. apostrophes to give meaning to the writing; multiple punctuation marks, which can be used when saving documents in Word on the computer.

Plagiarism is an intellectual fraud or academic offense that can have consequences. To avoid this, it is always necessary to cite the author in case one makes a reference and also to adopt a style that is an element of appreciation of coherence and consistency while

demonstrating to the US vs. UK English reader by emphasizing the differences between American and British English in terms of pronunciation, spelling, grammar, and usage.

Writing is knowing how to respect literature; this module allows me to start making papers while respecting the rules laid down by Euclid University, learning and mastering the rules in the academic course.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

The Bluebook. 2010. *A Uniform System of Citation*. 9th ed. Columbia Law Review Association, the Harvard Law Review Association, the University of Pennsylvania Law Review, and The Yale Law Journal.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Manvi, Manvi. 2020. "Writing Style you Should Know as a Writer." Accessed October 20, 2024. <https://writerena.com/writing-styles>.

Payne, Jeunese Adrienne. 2018. "Essay Writing Handbook." Accessed October 20, 2024. <https://www.cl.cam.ac.uk/teaching/1718/SWSecEng/essay-cst1a-2018.pdf>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.